

Opioid Use Disorder Crisis: Current State & Tenets to Recovery

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Introduction

- Opioid use disorder (OUD) is defined in the DSM-5 as a problematic pattern of opioid use leading to clinically significant impairment or distress.
- Opioid use disorder (OUD) can also be defined as a chronic disorder that, while primarily driven by stimulation of reward neurocircuits in the brain, gradually involves anti-reward neurocircuits, leading to adverse emotive states and deterioration. (Figure 2)
- The main objectives and intent of this study are represented in figure 1 as follows -

Figure 1: Mind Map of Objectives and Intent of Study

Method: Literature Search

A focused search and systematic review of literature on PubMed, Google Scholar, CDC, WHO was performed on January 30, 2024 with keywords including opioid use disorders, pharmacotherapy, health outcomes. Peer reviewed published articles from the years 2010 – 2024 were accessed as per PRISMA guidelines and analyzed and further evaluated for study purposes.

Clinical Presentations

The following clinical presentations were noted in people with OUD as grouped into 4 categories in table 1:

Acute Intoxication	Drowsiness, Decreased Awareness, Slow Speech, constricted Pupils
Harmful Use	Evidence of Physical Impairment or Psychological Impairment
Dependence	Symptoms fulfilling ICD-10 criteria are met
Overdose	Unconsciousness, Pinpoint Pupils, Respiration rate <6 breaths per minute

Table 1: Highlighting Clinical Presentations in patients with OUD

Etiology and Pathophysiology

- Dependence and addiction to opioids attributed to multiple factors including biological, genetic, environmental, and psychosocial.
- Opioids are prescribed for short-term pain management, but patients develop dependence/addiction due to over stimulation of reward and anti-reward neurocircuits, forcing many to continue taking them chronically.
- Abrupt stopping of opioids often leads to withdrawal symptoms in patients.
- Dependence on opioids develops rather swiftly, most likely due to changes in mu-opioid receptors, including signaling abnormalities, receptor desensitization, and internalization.

Figure 2: Diagram showing the Brain reward and Anti-reward Neurocircuits. (used with permission from Koob, G., Volkow, N, 2010)

Epidemiology

- Many users that inject drugs have a higher risk for HIV, Hepatitis B & C virus infections.
- Prescription opioid use is an important risk factor.
- Other factors include genetics, usage among peers, psychiatric disorders, family factors, educational level.
- Figure 3 highlights the global harm due to Opioid disorders.

Figure 3: The Global Harm due to Opioid Use Disorders

Evaluation

- A complete social and mental health history.
- History of trauma, injuries, previous hospitalizations, and surgeries to identify gateways for opioid use.
- History of drug use by injection: tests should be ordered to screen for HIV and hepatitis B and C.
- Urine drug screening for opioids.
- Screening tools such as ASSIST and CRAFFT should be used.

Figure 5: Common Opioids that are misused include - Codeine, Fentanyl

Screening Methods

- If continued use leads to significant impairment clinically, then patients meet the OUD criteria based on symptoms fulfilled by ICD-10 criteria
- Screening tools are critical in assessing and evaluating the people
- WHO has assessment tools for clinicians to help in screening of patients. One is the Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST)

Management

Figure 4: Flowchart Showing Management of Complications of Opioid Use Disorders

Treatment

Treatment of OUD tends to improve physical and psychological conditions. Multiple avenues for help and approaches to the rehabilitation and maintenance of patients with OUD are available, including

- Medical Treatment
- Counseling and Therapy
- Support Groups
- Naloxone Access
- Professional Help
- Emergency Services

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